

Modeling of inhibitory activity of indomethacin derivatives as COX-2 inhibitors through QSAR analysis[†]

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Abstract : Quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSAR) study has been performed on a series of indomethacin derivatives using topological and physicochemical parameters. Several QSAR equations were formulated through regression analysis by grouping these descriptors. It has been demonstrated that empirical parameters such as D, St, IOR along with indicator parameter have considerable effect on the inhibitory activity of these derivatives towards COX-2 enzyme. The best equation suggest is the tri-parametric model containing the parameters D, I₁, I₂ for modeling the activity of the compounds under present study and which was able to explain 81.3% of the variance in the data. The predictive ability of these equations was cross validated by evaluating the residual activity, cross validated R² values (R²_{CV}) by leave one out (LOO) technique.

Keywords : COX-2 inhibitor, indomethacin derivatives, QSAR, regression analysis.

Introduction

Various non-steroidal and anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are known for the inhibition of cyclooxygenases (COX) enzyme¹. COX is an enzyme responsible for the production of prostaglandins. COX-1 and COX-2 are two isoforms of COX, both isoform of this enzyme produce prostaglandins, prostacyclin, and thromboxanes by transformation of arachidonic acid. Prostaglandins produced by COX-1 is involved in housekeeping function, while prostaglandins produce by COX-2 contribute to inflammation. The primary effect of the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) is to inhibit cyclooxygenase (COX or prostaglandin synthase [PGHS]), thereby blocking the ultimate transformation of arachidonic acid to prostaglandins, prostacyclin, and thromboxanes². COX-2 selective inhibitor is a form of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) that directly targets COX-2, an enzyme responsible for inflammation and pain. Targeting COX-2 selectively reduces the risk of peptic ulceration, and is the main feature of celecoxib, rofecoxib and other members of this class of drugs. The development of selective inhibitors of COX-2 is an important target in order to reduce adverse side effects.

As part of our ongoing research efforts to discover

novel COX-2 inhibitors through QSAR analysis³⁻⁵, in the present work QSAR studies were performed on a set of 15 compounds of indomethacin derivatives. For this purpose we have taken the activities pIC₅₀ from literature which were reported by Wey and co-worker⁶. In this series COX-2 inhibitory activity has been expressed as IC₅₀ values in micro molar units which represents the concentration of drug that inhibits 50% of COX-2 enzyme. The values were converted to negative logarithms (pIC₅₀) in order to reduce the skewness of the data set and obtain a linear relationship in the QSAR equations.

Computational details :

Various derivatives of indomethacin were drawn on ACD Lab Chem Sketch version 10 software⁷ for calculation of various parameters such as molecular weight (Mw), molecular volume (Mv), molar refractivity (Mr), parachor (Pc), surface tension (st), density (D), index of refraction (IOR), polarizability (Pz) and partition coefficient (log P). However, most of the topological parameters such as balaban indices (J), wiener index (W), mean wiener index (WA), Balaban centric index (BAC) and molecular connectivity (χ); were calculated by using E Dragon software. The most common molecular file formats are ac-

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

cepted in E Dragon software are SMILES notations, which are created on line by Babel software and 2D structure of various derivatives, are converted into 3D optimized structures on-line using CORINA, provided by Molecular Networks GMBH.

Results and discussion

Several physicochemical and topological parameters were calculated for a series of indomethacin derivatives however, the descriptors such as surface tension (st), density (D) and index of refraction (IOR) have been found statistically significant for modeling of activity. The indicator parameters I_1 , I_2 have also been used which account for the $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHCONH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$ and $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHSO}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$ group respectively at R_1 position. Different analogues of parent structure with values of inhibitory activity and indicator parameters are reported in Table 1. All the parameters that were used for the present analysis are also listed in Table 1.

Hansch analysis⁸ was used for multi-parametric regression analysis using structural parameters and inhibi-

tory activity and was executed with SPSS (7.5) software. Multiple regression analysis resulted in several significant multi-parametric QSAR models. Descriptors that were selected for the final equation are those having inter-correlation coefficient below 0.5. A correlation matrix showing inter-correlation among all the parameters and also with the activity is presented in Table 2.

Significant model obtained in the present analysis are given below :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pIC}_{50} = & -5.100 (\pm 1.819)\text{D} \\ & -0.643 (\pm 0.504)\text{I}_1 \\ & +0.533 (\pm 0.512)\text{I}_2 + 12.579 \\ n = 15, R = 0.902, R^2 = 0.813, R^2_A = 0.762, SE = & \\ 0.221, F_{(3,11)} = 15.953, Q = 4.081 & \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{pIC}_{50} = & -0.074 (\pm 0.032)\text{St} \\ & -0.564 (\pm 0.577)\text{I}_1 \\ & +0.542 (\pm 0.586)\text{I}_2 + 9.414 \\ n = 15, R = 0.870, R^2 = 0.757, R^2_A = 0.690, SE = & \\ 0.252, F_{(3,11)} = 11.396, Q = 3.452 & \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

Table 1. Structural detail with biological activity, indicator parameters and value of others parameters for series of indomethacin derivatives

Sr. No.	R_1	R_2	R_3	pIC_{50}	IOR	ST	D	I_1	I_2
1.	CH_2COCH_3	OCH_3	H	6.155	1.619	47.400	1.320	0	0
2.	CH_2COCH_3	OH	H	5.301	1.651	53.500	1.400	0	0
3.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$	OH	H	5.456	1.640	56.700	1.420	0	0
4.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$	OSO_2NH_2	H	4.580	1.659	64.400	1.550	0	0
5.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$	OH	H	5.523	1.633	51.500	1.340	0	0
6.	CH_2COOH	OCH_3	Cl	5.387	1.629	48.600	1.400	0	0
7.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$	OCH_3	Cl	5.237	1.624	52.300	1.420	0	0
8.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONH}(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{OH}$	OCH_3	H	5.921	1.601	46.000	1.260	0	0
9.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$	OCH_3	H	5.745	1.607	46.700	1.280	0	0
10.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$	OCH_3	H	5.921	1.615	51.400	1.360	0	0
11.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONHCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{ONO}_2$	OCH_3	H	5.921	1.597	47.700	1.300	0	0
12.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CONHO}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$	OCH_3	H	6.155	1.602	47.200	1.310	0	0
13.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHCONH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$	OCH_3	H	5.000	1.618	52.000	1.360	1	0
14.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHSO}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$	OCH_3	H	5.921	1.627	54.500	1.410	0	1
15.	$\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHSO}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$	OCH_3	H	5.959	1.614	50.000	1.340	0	0

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$$\begin{aligned} \text{pIC}_{50} = & -19.267 (\pm 8.346)\text{IOR} \\ & -7.20 (\pm 0.583)\text{I}_1 \\ & +0.374 (\pm 0.584)\text{I}_2 + 36.894 \end{aligned}$$

$$n = 15, R = 0.867, R^2 = 0.751, R^2_A = 0.683, SE = 0.255, F_{(3,11)} = 11.054, Q = 3.400 \quad (3)$$

Here, n = total number of compounds, R = correlation coefficient, R_2 = coefficient of determination, R^2_A = adjusted coefficient of determination, SE = standard error of estimate, F = variance ratio^{9,10}, Q = quality of fit^{11,12}.

Table 2. Correlation matrix between different parameters

	pIC ₅₀	ST	D	IOR	I ₁	I ₂
pIC ₅₀	1.000					
ST	-0.738	1.000				
D	-0.757	0.928	1.000			
IOR	-0.725	0.842	0.860	1.000		
I ₁	-0.374	0.039	-0.018	-0.067	1.000	
I ₂	0.189	0.183	0.173	0.071	-0.071	1.000

Above QSAR model shows that coefficient of D , St and IOR are negative suggesting that decrease in the value of these parameters may enhance the activity of indomethacine derivatives to inhibit COX-2 enzyme. Negative coefficient of I_1 suggest that $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHCONH}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$ group at R_1 position contribute negatively while positive coefficient of I_2 suggests that $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NHSO}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{ONO}_2$ group at R_1 position is favorable for the activity.

The significance and quality of these models was checked on the basis of the values of “ R ”, “ R^2 ”, “ R^2_A ”, quality factor “ Q ”, standard error of estimate “ SE ”. Amongst all these statistically significant models discussed above model (1) is the best model since the values of $R = 0.902$, $R^2 = 0.813$, $R^2_A = 0.762$ are the best as compared to all the other models. In order to confirm that the model with excellent statistics has also excellent prediction power too, we have evaluated quality factor Q . The predictive power as determined by the Pogliani Q parameter for the model (1) [$Q = 4.081$] confirms that this model has excellent statistics as well as excellent predictive power. The calculated F value is greater than F theoretical value [$F_{(3,11)} = 3.590$], the value of standard error of estimate is the lowest and the low $SE = 0.221$

confirms that equation statistically significant and excellent model and it has been found to be having outstanding predictive power also.

Predicted and residual activity values for model (1) are given in Table 3. Predicted values are the calculated activities obtained from model (1) and the residual values are the difference between the observed biological activities and calculated activities. In order to examine the relative potential models, predictive correlation coefficient (R^2_{Pred}) were estimated by plotting graphs between observed and calculated IC_{50} values obtained with the help of model (1). Such correlations are shown in Fig. 1.

Table 3. Comparison between observed and predicted activities and their residual values

Sr. No.	Observed activity	Eq. (1)	
		Predicted activity	Residual
1.	6.155	5.847	0.308
2.	5.301	5.439	-0.138
3.	5.456	5.337	0.119
4.	4.580	4.674	-0.094
5.	5.523	5.745	-0.222
6.	5.387	5.439	-0.052
7.	5.237	5.337	-0.100
8.	5.921	6.153	-0.232
9.	5.745	6.051	-0.306
10.	5.921	5.643	0.278
11.	5.921	5.949	-0.028
12.	6.155	5.898	0.257
13.	5.000	5.000	0.000
14.	5.921	5.921	0.000
15.	5.959	5.745	0.214

Fig. 1. A plot showing comparison between observed and predicted activity based on eq. (1).

Table 4. Cross validated parameters and predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE) for the proposed model

Model No.	n	Parameter used	PRESS	SSY	PRESS/SSY	R ² _{CV}	PSE	R	1-R ²	PE	6PE
(1)	15	D + 11 + 12	0.536	2.333	0.230	0.770	0.189	0.902	0.187	0.032	0.193
(2)	15	St + 11 + 12	0.699	2.171	0.322	0.678	0.216	0.870	0.243	0.041	0.251
(3)	15	IOR + 11 + 12	0.715	2.155	0.332	0.668	0.218	0.867	0.249	0.043	0.257

The cross validation analysis was performed using leave one out (LOO) method¹³, in which one compound is removed from the data set and the activity is correlated using the rest of the data. The cross-validated R² in each case was found to be very close to the value of R² for the entire data set and hence these models can be termed as statistically significant. Cross validation provides the values of PRESS, SSY, PSE, R²_{CV} and R²_A from which we can test the predictive power of the proposed model. The predictive error of coefficient of correlation (PE)¹⁴ is another parameter used to decide the predictive power of the proposed models. PRESS, SSY, PSE, R²_{CV}, R²_A and PE value of all the proposed model were calculated and they are reported in Table 4.

It is argued that if the value R < PE, then such correlation is not significant; however if value of R > PE by several times (at least three times), then the parameters are correlated. However, if value of R > 6PE, then mathematically the correlation is unquestionably good. For the models (1) developed here the condition R > 6PE is satisfied and hence this model can be said to have good predictive power.

Conclusion

The present study was performed to examine the suitability of the empirical parameters for correlating the biological activity of a series of indomethacin derivatives which are known as potent COX-2 inhibitors through QSAR analysis.

QSAR model (1) optimized with empirical parameters with high statistical quality (R = 0.902, R² = 0.813) suggests that indomethacin derivatives having -CH₂CH₂NHSO₂(CH₂)₃ONO₂ group at R₁ position with low value of density (D) are more favorable as COX-2 inhibitor.

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